

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D10.3

First Mid-term Dissemination

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Aliance for Internet of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Comission
EU	European Union
EUROCAE	European Organization for Civil Aviation Equipment
GSA	European GNSS Agency
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
KOM	Kick-off meeting
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable contains the first report of the activities carried out within PILOTING to promote and disseminate the project and its main results, based on the objectives defined in the D10.2 Exploitation and Dissemination Plan.

1.2 Scope of the document

The D10.3 First-Mid Dissemination Report deliverable covers the activities carried out within task T10.3 Dissemination, communication, and engaging the I&M community in the first reporting period of the project, mainly focused on achieving the policy maker, industry and end-user as well as scientific and technical communities engagement.

Table 2 shows the target audience groups identified within the project and the dissemination activities undertaken in this period (M1-M18) with each one.

Target group	Dissemination and communication channels
End users	European end-user symposiums (see section 3.4), professional, specialised websites/web-portals magazines (see section 3.2), and talks organised for specialised audiences (see sections 0).
Scientific/ research communities	Posters and talks at international conferences (see section 3.4), workshops and exhibitions (see section 3.3); Peer-reviewed journal publications (see section 3.2)
Industry	Through Digital Innovation Hubs (like RIMA), clusters and professional fair shows (see section 0), and talks organised for specialised audiences. Three workshops with PILOTING User group members are planned in M6, M32 y M48.
Public Institutions	EC institutions (EASA, GSA, etc.) and communications to National institutions (see Sections 3.3 and 3.4).
Standardisation entities	Standardisation entities like EUROCAE, AIOTI, API, IEC, OGC, etc. (see Section 3.2).
General public	Press releases (see section 2.4), project website (see section 2.2), workshops (see section 0) and social media (see section 2.3).

Table 2. Dissemination channels, according to the identified target group.

1.3 Structure of the document

This report has been structured according to the dissemination/communication tools defined in the deliverable D10.2 to each target audience group:

- Section 1 describes the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 aims to present the main communication activities carried out within the PILOTING project.

- Section 3 presents the main dissemination actions within the PILOTING project in the M1-M18 period.
- Section 4 presents the status of the KPIs defined in the D10.2.
- Section 5 summarises the main conclusions of the First-Mid Dissemination Report.

2. Communication tools

2.1 Visual Identity

As mentioned in the D10.2, within the PILOTING Dissemination Strategy, a coherent identity has been developed for all publications and presentations related to the project. The visual identity includes the project logo (see Figure 1), flyer (see Annex I: Flyer layout), roll-up (see Annex II: Roll-up layout), poster (see Annex III: Poster layout) and templates (to documents and presentations) used when the partners have presented their work.

Figure 1. PILOTING logo.

This material is reviewed and updated during the execution of the PILOTING project. For example, up to M18, two PILOTING partners have changed the name of their companies. Therefore, the flyer, roll-up, poster, and templates have been modified to include the new company's logos (see Annexes).

2.2 Project Website

The project website (<https://pilotng-project.eu/>) was launched in January 2020 and is one of the most important communication channels of PILOTING.

The project consortium uses the website to disseminate the main project research progress, findings, outputs and activities. The PILOTING webpage has been structured in five main sections (see Figure 2):

Figure 2. PILOTING project website: “Home” tab.

- a) Home: This section summarizes the main project objectives and the latest project’s news.
- b) Project overview: The purpose, challenges and objectives of the PILOTING project are included.
- c) Consortium, where each consortium members are described.
- d) News: This section shows the main project results achieved, PILOTING dissemination activities, project newsletters and any new project action undertaken within the project.
- e) Public Material, which has two main sub-sections: 1. Multimedia, where all the videos and podcast developed within the project are uploaded; and 2. Publication and datasets, which it is linked with the PILOTING Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/piloting/>), open access repository where all public deliverables, publications and datasets are being uploaded.

In addition, the website provides a contact point for the different target groups of the PILOTING project, the email address: piloting-project@catec.aero.

Figure 3 shows as the average of PILOTING website audience has increased from M1 to M18.

Figure 3. PILOTING website statistics.

As Table 3 shows, most of the visits are from consortium countries, demonstrating the PILOTING partners’ efforts to disseminate the project.

Country	Clicks	Impressions
Spain	290	4.287
Greece	104	3.064
United Kingdom	41	5.381
Switzerland	40	2.713
Netherlands	38	1.553
Germany	35	2.598
France	34	2.164
Italy	32	2.203
United States	21	7.406
Japan	21	842

Table 3. PILOTING website: Origin of visits

2.3 Social media

PILOTING has been promoted through different social media channels, which have been created to maximise the impact and visibility to project events and news in the general public. In particular, PILOTING has established the following social media profiles:

- **PILOTING LinkedIn profile**

LinkedIn is a social network designed for the professional community, which has enabled to establish a network with most of the PILOTING target audience as bridge/tunnels/refineries owners/managers/operators, research institutes, individuals, and entities involved in any of the fields related to PILOTING.

The PILOTING LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/h2020-piloting-project/>, see Figure 4) was launched at the end of 2019 and, since then, has been in a constant increase both in posts and followers.

Figure 4. PILOTING LinkedIn Profile.

At the timing of drafting this document, PILOTING LinkedIn Profile had 339 followers. The following graph (Figure 5) shows the evolution of new LinkedIn followers in the last 12 months.

Figure 5. New followers of the PILOTING LinkedIn profile in the last 12 months of the project.

Finally, Figure 6 shows the views of the PILOTING LinkedIn profile in the last 12 months of the project. The highest peaks are related to the dissemination actions addressed by the PILOTING consortium: launching an episode of the PILOTING Youtube Series or PILOTING podcast, post an event where a PILOTING partner has presented the project or dissemination of the main project's outcomes.

Figure 6. Views of the PILOTING LinkedIn profile in the last 12 months of the Project.

- **PILOTING Twitter account**

Twitter PILOTING account (https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU, see Figure 7) was also launched at the end of 2019 and mainly used to disseminate results and other news related to the project.

Twitter is a more flexible platform that has allowed to maintain close contact with the general public through posting news, status updates, links to multimedia content and more in real-time. At the time of drafting this document, PILOTING Twitter Profile has 261 followers.

During the M1-M18 PILOTING period, an average of 4 tweets per week has been posted, surpassing the objective defined in the DoA.

Figure 7. PILOTING Twitter Profile.

The Project Coordinator, CATEC, manages PILOTING’s social media profiles.

The PILOTING’s consortium efforts to disseminate the initiative has been really successful, and the PILOTING project has achieved the target value of followers in the social networks defined in the “D10.2 Exploitation and Dissemination Plan” (Target Value: 500; Achieved Value: 600).

2.4 Periodic press-releases

PILOTING consortium has published periodic press releases where specific PILOTING’s achievements that can be interesting to the industrial companies, SEMs and the general public has been presented.

The press release coordinators launched these project's press releases (see Table 4) in each PILOTING's country to national and/or international, electronic and printed media.

Spain	FERROVIAL
Greece	ICCS
Switzerland	WTR
France	CHEVRON
Netherlands	APPLUS RVIS
Norway	SINTEF

Table 4. Press release coordinator per country

Table 5 shows the news/articles disseminated through the PILOTING consortium countries in M1-M18 period.

Partner	Country	Date	Topic	Venue	Evidence
CATEC	Spain	17/01/2020	PILOTING project officially starts with its KOM	Electronic Media: International Newspaper	https://www.europapress.es/andalucia/noticia-proyecto-europeo-coordinado-andalucia-impulsa-tecnologia-robotica-mejorar-mantenimiento-infraestructuras-20200117173627.html
CATEC	Spain	20/01/2020	PILOTING project officially starts with its KOM	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.obrasurbanas.es/piloting/ http://www.hondurasensusmanos.info/2020/01/20/tecnologia-robotica-para-mejorar-las-tareas-de-inspeccion-y-mantenimiento-de-infraestructuras-civiles-envejecidas https://www.interempresas.net/ObrasPublicas/Articulos/263049-Tecnologia-robotica-mejorar-tareas-inspeccion-mantenimiento-infraestructuras-civiles.html
CATEC	Spain	22/01/2020	PILOTING presentation	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.diariodesevilla.es/tecnologia/Robotica-inspeccionar-infraestructuras-envejecidas_0_1430257317.html https://www.pressreader.com/spain/diario-de-cadiz/20200122/282196537915511 https://www.diariodejerez.es/tecnologia/Robotica-inspeccionar-infraestructuras-envejecidas_0_1430257317.html

					https://www.diariodealmeria.es/tecnologia/Robotica-inspeccionar-infraestructuras-envejecidas_0_1430257317.html
INLECOM	Greece	01/06/2020	Article on the digital magazine of “Innovation, Research & Technology” (Issue #118, Spring-Summer 2020)	Electronic Magazine	http://www.ekt.gr/el/magazines/24396
APPLUS RVIS	Netherlands	13/10/2020	PILOTING 1 st Project stakeholders webinar	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.kint.nl/nieuws/europese-bedrijven-werken-samen-aan-robotoplossingen-voor-de-inspectie-en-maintenance-branche-(i-and-m).html
ICCS	Greece	19/10/2020	PILOTING 1 st Project stakeholders webinar	ICCS website	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/news/press/item/1802-piloting-webinar
ICCS	Greece	3/12/2020	PILOTING project demonstrations in the Metsovo Tunnel in Greece	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/images/press/athina984.pdf https://i-sense.iccs.gr/images/press/Ypodomes.pdf https://i-sense.iccs.gr/images/press/Michanikos_Online.pdf https://i-sense.iccs.gr/images/press/EnergyFeed.gr.pdf https://i-sense.iccs.gr/images/press/EnergyIn.pdf
SINTEF	Norway	09/12/2020	PILOTING project demonstrations in the Metsovo Tunnel in Greece	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.at.no/anlegg/539041
SINTEF	Norway	10/12/2020	PILOTING project demonstrations in the Metsovo Tunnel in Greece	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.samferdselinfra.no/sender-roboter-for-a-fikse-tunneler/

SINTEF	Norway	10/12/2020	PILOTING project demonstrations in the Metsovo Tunnel in Greece	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.firdatidend.no/nyhende/robotar-skal-sjekka-tunnelar-og-vegar/
SINTEF	Norway	12/12/2020	PILOTING project demonstrations in the Metsovo Tunnel in Greece	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.nationen.no/article/robotar-skal-sjekka-tunnelar-og-vegar/
SINTEF	Norway	14/12/2020	PILOTING 1 st Project stakeholders webinar	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.adressa.no/mn24/2020/12/14/Skal-finne-ut-om-roboter-kan-ta-over-farlig-arbeid-23141237.ece
SINTEF	Norway	14/12/2020	PILOTING 1 st Project stakeholders webinar	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://www.tungt.no/article/view/768141/roboter-skal-fikse-tunneler
USE	Spain	December 2020	Drones inspired by the “mythological griffin”	Printed Media	Article about the latest USE developments in drones technologies and on its participation in H2020 European project, including PILOTING.
WTR	Switzerland	27/01/2021	WTR’s role and last developments within PILOTING project	Electronic Media: Local Journal	https://www.ndt.net/search/docs.php?id=25682
CATEC	Spain	28/02/2021	CATEC/USE participation in PILOTING project	Electronic Media: Local Media	https://fundaciondescubre.es/noticias/28f-la-fortaleza-de-la-ciencia-en-andalucia-en-la-era-post-covid/
CATEC	Spain	04/04/2021	PILOTING is presented in an interview with the project coordinator, Antidio Viguria	Electronic/ Printed Media: Local Media	https://sevilla.abc.es/sevilla/sevi-tras-mejores-universidades-mundo-cuenta-sevilla-podemos-igual-buenos-202104040828_noticia.html
CATEC	Spain	23/06/2021	Antidio Viguria presents CATEC capabilities and the main technologies that the research centre	Spanish National TV channel	https://7tvandalucia.es/andalucia/espacio-innovacion/3-31-antidio-viguria-catec-y-juan-jose-calvente-aertec/60403/

			developed, including those developed within PILOTING		
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Table 5. Local media presence.

Finally, it is important to highlight that PILOTING press coordinators have tried to disseminate PILOTING through other local media which have not published the press release. However, these actions carry value for dissemination because expert groups have been informed about PILOTING through PILOTING partners.

2.5 Electronic newsletters

Electronic newsletters have been periodically designed every six months, providing updates and relevant information. As shown in Table 6, two PILOTING newsletter issues have been published during this period.

Issue	Topics	Publication date	Partners responsible
1st newsletter	Overview of PILOTING project	August 2020	CATEC-Overall Coordination All partners- Contribution
2nd newsletter	Activities carried out by PILOTING consortium during the 2nd half of 2020	January 2021	CATEC-Overall Coordination All partners- Contribution

Table 6. Overview of newsletters.

At the time of writing this deliverable, we are finalizing the third newsletter that will be published during July 2021.

Dissemination paths

The newsletters have been disseminated through the PILOTING website ('NEWS tab'), PILOTING social networks and the PILOTING User Group that currently counts with more than 210 members (see Section 3.1).

2.6 New Communication Channels

The covid-19 pandemic has had a high impact on dissemination activities planned at the beginning of the project. Most of the planned dissemination actions identified by PILOTING partners were physical and international events, therefore, these have been cancelled or celebrated virtually due to the sanitary restrictions. This situation has led to a loss of personal contact between the different actors in the I&M community.

PILOTING consortium has defined new communications channels to compensate for the pandemic effects and maximise the PILOTING impact, disseminating the latest developments more visually.

2.6.1 Youtube Series Video: “Meet Our Inspection Robots”

The variety of inspection and maintenance operations considered in PILOTING requires the use of different robotic systems. Then, a series of robotic vehicles from PILOTING partners are being adapted/developed and integrated within the PILOTING I&M platform.

As a new communication channel, the PILOTING consortium is developing a Youtube Series Video focused on introducing each developed robot within the project to bring them closer to the I&M community.

This Youtube Series will be available through the [PILOTING website multimedia section](#) and the PILOTING social networks ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)). Table 7 summarises which “Meet Our Inspection Robots” episodes have been published in the M1-M18 period.

Episode	Publication date	Vehicle	Partners responsible
Episode 1	03/03/2021	Aerial contact drone - AeroX	CATEC
Episode 2	30/04/2021	CART robot	RBNK
Episode 3	25/05/2021	BIKE robot	WTR

Table 7. Public episodes of PILOTING Youtube Series: “Meet our inspections robots”

This Youtube Series will continue during the second period in order to present the different robotic vehicles that are being developed during the project.

2.6.2 Podcast Series: “PILOTING Inspection gadget”

PILOTING consortium has also decided to develop a podcast series with interviews with key people in the I&M sector.

These podcasts aim to obtain feedback from the I&M community and positioning the PILOTING consortium as a reference in the development of robotic solutions for I&M applications.

This Podcast Series “PILOTING Inspection Gadget” is available through the [PILOTING iVoox profile](#), the [PILOTING website multimedia section](#) and the PILOTING social networks ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)). Table 8 summarises which “PILOTING Inspection gadget” episodes have been published in the M1-M18 period.

Episode	Publication date	Topic
Episode 1	23/02/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 1 , Angelos Amditis and Konstantinos Bouklas from ICCS present RESIST H2020 project (https://www.resistproject.eu/).
Episode 2	29/03/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 2 , Adam Serblowski (Robotics Theme Lead – Surveillance Robotics from SHELL) gives his opinion about the potential benefits in the application of robotic and AI technologies to the I&M sector
Episode 3	26/04/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 3 , Antidio Viguria, PILOTING Project’s Manager, talks with Carlos Martín and Pablo

		Ramón, CEO and Software engineering at VES (Vertical Engineering Solutions, https://vengineering.com), respectively. VES, a spin-off company from Spain, is specialised in the application of drones to Inspection and maintenance, including industrial plants and civil infrastructure, achieving significant cost savings, increasing safety and improving efficiency, including reductions over time of Inspection.
Episode 4	17/05/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 4 , we interview Prof. Vincenzo Lippiello, full professor at the Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II and CEO Neabotics (https://www.neabotics.com/), spin-off funded to fully explore the transfer capabilities between the academy and the industry to the development of drone applications in the I&M sector.
Episode 5	14/06/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 5 , we talk with Tjibbe Bouma, Chairmain of the Board of SPRINT Robotic (https://www.sprintrobotics.org/), industry driven initiative that promotes the development, the availability, and the application of robotics techniques in technical inspections and maintenance of capital intensive infrastructure.

Table 8. Public episodes of PILOTING Podcast Series:” Inspection Gadget”

Also, this Podcast series will continue during the second period, as it has been shown an interesting tool to engage with different stakeholder of the I&M community and even to increase the coordination with other H2020 projects related to I&M.

3. Dissemination tools

3.1 PILOTING User Group

As defined in the PILOTING proposal, a list of contacts, the PILOTING User Group, has been created with all partners’ valuable contribution to reaching a large set of external entities and stakeholders.

The PILOTING User Group have been used to disseminate PILOTING latest developments, spread invitations to PILOTING events and disseminate information about other related EU projects.

The information sent to the PILOTING User Group is managed by CATEC through the email address piloting-project@catec.aero. However, all PILOTING partners can share any information through the PILOTING User Group contacting the Innovation, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (IDEM).

The PILOTING User Group list remains updated and accessible to all consortium partners in the project repository, Basecamp, in the file: Docs&Files → WP10 Exploitation, communication and dissemination → PILOTING User Group → PILOTING User Group list.

Finally, it is essential to highlight that PILOTING User Group consists of 212 members up to M18. Therefore, the target value defined in the proposal (150) has been achieved.

3.2 Publications

Within PILOTING, the project's main were disseminated through scientific publications in various journals and conferences. A list of the scientific publications during the M1-M18 period is presented in Table 9.

The scientific publications are provided in Green Open access. All publications are uploaded on Zenodo PILOTING Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/piloting/>).

TITLE	ABSTRACT	AUTHORS	INVOLVED INSTITUTIONS	REFERENCE	CATEGORY	PUB. DATE	STATUS
Fully-Actuated Aerial Manipulator for Infrastructure Contact Inspection: Design, Modeling, Localisation, and Control	This paper presents the design, modeling and control of a fully actuated aerial robot for infrastructure contact inspection as well as its localisation system. Health assessment of transport infrastructure involves measurements with sensors in contact with the bridge and tunnel surfaces and the installation of monitoring sensing devices at specific points. The design of the aerial robot presented in the paper includes a 3DoF lightweight arm with a sensorized passive joint which can measure the contact force to regulate the force applied with the sensor on the structure. The aerial platform has been designed with tilted propellers to be fully actuated, achieving independent attitude and position control. It also mounts a “docking gear” to establish full contact with the infrastructure during the inspection, minimising the measurement errors derived from the motion of the aerial platform and allowing full contact with the surface regardless of its condition (smooth, rough, ...). The localisation system of the aerial robot uses multi-sensor fusion of the measurements of a topographic laser sensor on the ground and a tracking camera and inertial sensors on-board the aerial robot, to be able to fly under the bridge deck or close to the bridge pillars where GNSS satellite signals are not available. The paper also presents the modeling and control of the aerial robot. Validation experiments of the localisation system and the control system, and with the aerial robot inspecting a real bridge are also included.	Pedro J. Sanchez-Cuevas, Antonio Gonzalez-Morgado, Nicolas Cortes ,Diego B. Gayango ,Antonio E. Jimenez-Cano ,Aníbal Ollero and Guillermo Heredia	USE	Journal: MDPI DOI: https://doi.org/10.3390/s20174708	Journal Paper	20th August 2020	Published
Aerial robot for contact bridge inspection	This paper aims to present AeroX UAV platform, a new concept of an aerial robotic system that is able to perform industrial contact inspections. This aerial platform incorporates a novel mechanical device that allows maintaining contact, both vertically and horizontally, and even in difficult environmental	Miguel Ángel Trujillo, Ángel Luis Petrus, Daniel Martínez Campos, Francisco Javier Garrido, Antidio	CATEC/USE	2020 CivilDron Conference https://zenodo.org/record/424	Conference Paper	15/16 December 2020	Published

	conditions. In this paper, the AeroX solution is discussed over the whole dissertation, presenting the results for a real case performed on a real bridge. The AeroX will be one of the robotic systems considered to adapt in PILOTING project (H2020-ICT-2019-2,871542) to mature its novel technology and getting closer to the market.	Viguria and Anibal Ollero		6276#.YEs8wFVKiCh			
PHASER: A Robust and Correspondence-Free Global Pointcloud Registration	We propose PHASER, a correspondence-free global registration of sensor-centric pointclouds that is robust to noise, sparsity, and partial overlaps. Our method can seamlessly handle multimodal information, and does not rely on keypoint nor descriptor preprocessing modules. By exploiting properties of Fourier analysis, PHASER operates directly on the sensor's signal, fusing the spectra of multiple channels and computing the 6-DoF transformation based on correlation. Our registration pipeline starts by finding the most likely rotation $r \in SO(3)$ followed by computing the most likely translation $t \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Both estimates, r , and t are distributed according to a probability distribution that takes the underlying manifold into account, i.e., a Bingham and a Gaussian distribution, respectively. This further allows our approach to consider the periodic-nature of r and naturally represents its uncertainty. We extensively compare PHASER against several well-known registration algorithms on both simulated datasets, and real-world data acquired using different sensor configurations. Our results show that PHASER can globally align pointclouds in less than 100 ms with an average accuracy of 2 cm and 0.5° , is resilient against noise, and can handle partial overlap.	Lukas Bernreiter; Lionel Ott; Juan Nieto; Roland Siegwart; Cesar Cadena	ETHZ	Journal: IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters DOI: 10.1109/LRA.2021.3052418	Journal Paper	18th January 2021	Published
Motorway Tunnels Resilience Through Automated	In years where most of the road infrastructures are severely ageing worldwide, but still enormously contributing to transportation smoothness (people, cargo, etc.), careful monitoring attention is needed in mind of climate/weather change (extreme events,	Konstantinos Loupos, Thomas Krousarlis	INLECOM	Publication at PIARC Conference (WORLD WINTER	Conference Paper ABSTRACT ACCEPTED	7-11, February 2022	https://www.piarc-calgary2022.org/

Deformation Monitoring	<p>natural/man-made disasters, material aging, etc.) and capacity needs increase (increased flows for users). These factors are contributing to the overall network resilience as it is an important contributor to their long-term sustainability. Sustainability of the road network directly affects economical, social and environmental aspects that indicate the overall value of their resilience and the urgent needs for adaptations, monitoring, risk management/analysis and forecasting, but also effective vulnerability modelling and assessment approaches. In the later dimension, this publication presents recent research results on a 3D modelling system for measuring deformations in highway tunnels using 3D laser imaging sensors and consolidating the results in an approach to early detect deformations and system deteriorations over time. The system is able to perform analysis of a 3D model of the infrastructure at millimeter level and provide comparisons with existing (previous) models to detect abnormalities in the 3D shape of the tunnel (intrados) as results of partial deformations. Early indication of any infrastructure deterioration is pinpointed and georeferenced for immediate uptake in the maintenance planning of highway safety teams and maintenance personnel including 3D geometrical information on the defect position. The system is supported by an autonomous navigating robotic system that is able to position the sensing devices at particular inspection points of interest or the suitable points for a holistic infrastructure measurement/modelling. The publication includes sensor and platform integration, data management, configuration, robotic control, performance validation, testing and deployment of the system at actual road infrastructures. This research presents results from the running, EC co-funded, research project, PILOTING (https://piloting-project.eu/) currently during its 2nd year of execution over robotic</p>			SERVICE AND ROAD RESILIENCE CONGRESS)		
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	inspection for the oil & gas and transport infrastructures.						
Aerial Robotic System for Complete Bridge Inspections	<p>Bridge inspections have a large variety of procedures to ensure the safety of its facilities and personnel, and at the same time tightly budget constraints. These procedures involve extensive inspections, most of which should be performed at height and using both cameras and other sensors that require to be in contact with the surfaces being inspected. Then, bridge inspections traditionally require access to specific inspection points using man-lifts, cranes, scaffolds, or rope-access techniques, which increments importantly the costs of these inspections.</p> <p>This work will present a system formed by two drones that will perform complete inspection operations in bridges in less time, reducing costs, improving quality of the inspection, and increasing safety of operators. The first one is an aerial robot that can obtain pictures of the overall bridge fully autonomously thanks to a non-GPS navigation system. The second one is the AeroX drone platform, a novel solution for inspection of difficult access areas. The AeroX can perform contact inspection due to its robotic contact device, which is equipped with an end-effector. Finally, both drones will be presented with videos of the validation experiments.</p>	M. A. Trujillo, A. L. Petrus, D. Martinez, F. J. Garrido, A. Viguria and A. Ollero	CATEC	Publication at IRF2021 Conference	Conference paper Submitted and waiting for acceptance notification	November 7-10, 2021	https://worldmeeting.info/global/

Table 9. Papers published in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings

Finally, Table 10 shows the contributions to publications related with new standards.

TITLE	Description of the publication	INVOLVED INSTITUTIONS	PUB. DATE	Venue
ED-280 Guidelines for UAS safety analysis for the Specific category (low and medium levels of robustness)	Contribution to EUROCAE WG-105. This document contains guidelines for a UAS operator or manufacturer in order to obtain the evidences that the UAS is designed considering system safety and reliability and perform the required safety analyses to fulfil part of OSO#5 requirements, for low and medium level of robustness, as part of the SORA risk assessment under the Specific category of EASA drone regulation.	CATEC	Dic-2020	ED-280 Guidelines for UAS safety analysis for the Specific category (low and medium levels of robustness)
AIOTI WG03 - Beyond 5G: enabling technologies and challenges	Contribution to AIOTI Working Group 03 - IoT and 5G on a consolidated report on 5G challenges and applications. The use case provided was related to autonomous robotic inspection of highways' infrastructures.	INLECOM	Pending release	Online

Table 10. Articles published in relation with PILOTING project.

3.3 Organisation of workshops

One of PILOTING's dissemination activities is organising workshops to obtain feedback from the I&M community.

Within PILOTING, three workshops were originally planned: one initial workshop to present the PILOTING requirements identified and two workshops (at M32 and M48) to present the main PILOTING results.

Table 11 shows the four workshops organised within the PILOTING project in this period.

Workshop	Description	Date	Attendees	Results
Aerial Intelligent Robotics For Inspection And Maintenance workshop at ERF 2020	<p>The main aims of this workshop is to present the interest in the application of aerial robotics, combined with artificial intelligence methods, for inspection and maintenance. Methods such as learning and autonomous detection will be applied to provide intelligence to aerial robots in inspection and maintenance applications. It includes the perception and high-level control of aerial robots, as well as the exploitation of data for the inspection and maintenance application.</p> <p>The Workshop also presented recent results and demonstrations of on-going H2020 projects related to the application of aerial robotics to inspection and maintenance, including HYFLIERS, AERIAL-CORE, PILOTING, RESIST and GRIFFIN, as well as other successful projects recently finalized such as AEROARMS.</p> <p>This workshop was co-organised by A. Ollero (USE) and A. Viguria (CATEC) with Mauricio Calva (Chevron), Kris Kydd (TOTAL) and Juha Rönning (University of Oulu). The Workshop had 9 presentations, two Round Table and an interactive session. USE, FADA-CATEC, delivered presentations. USE also chaired a round table.</p>	3 rd March 2020	>50 attendees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60% Scientific /research community (Universities, research centres, etc) • 40% Industry/End-users from the I&M sector 	<p>This workshop continued a very successful series, which have been very well attended in all previous workshops in the last three years. This series of workshops has served to generate new joint initiatives and successful proposals (like PILOTING project itself).</p> <p>One of the outcomes of this workshop was to get feedback from the industry (end-users), and other stakeholders, about the way they see the use of AI-based technologies in the I&M sector. It was concluded that AI should be seen as a support tool, in order to perform a first refinement of the complete obtained data from the robotic vehicles (which is usually very large). However, the last decision to classify a defect should be confirmed by a qualified inspector.</p> <p>This feedback was very important in the design phase of the PILOTING I&M platform, and in fact, the current approach for the integration of AI-based algorithms in the PILOTING I&M platform follows this strategy.</p>
1st PILOTING stakeholder's workshop	<p>The 1st PILOTING workshop was targeted to asset owners, inspection service providers, robotics companies interested in the inspection and maintenance industry, and any other industrial actor interested in this kind of industry.</p>	25 th June 2020	>150 attendees from a hundred companies	<p>This workshop has allowed to obtain feedback about the end-user requirements, along with the functional specifications of the PILOTING I&M platform and the results of the SoEL studies.</p>

	<p>This workshop presented the 9 cases of use of inspection tasks that have been identified within the project with the help of the end-users companies of these robotic systems: Ferroviario (Spain), Chevron Oronite (France) and Egnatia Odos AE (Greece). In addition, the functional requirements of the PILOTING system (consisting of robotic vehicles, AI algorithms, and interconnected information systems) have been defined to meet all standards.</p> <p>26 countries attended this virtual meeting, 8 of them from outside Europe (Brazil, Canada, Japan, Mexico, USA, Turkey, Singapore and Saudi Arabia) .</p> <p>This workshop was organised virtually through Livestorm platform due to the pandemic. Figure 10 shows the event’s agenda.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 26,5% End-user or Asset owner • 14,7% Industrial technological developer • 2,9% Inspection Service provider • 5,9% Robotic System developer • 50% University/research center 	<p>In addition, in order to identify the PILOTING uses cases of greatest interest to the industry, the following surveys were conducted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which use cases are you mostly interested in? <div data-bbox="1485 435 2063 775"> <table border="1"> <caption>Which use cases are you mostly interested in?</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Use Case</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Refinery - ground monitoring</td> <td>7</td> <td>15,9 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Refinery - inspection of large...</td> <td>13</td> <td>29,5 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Refinery - pipe inspections</td> <td>20</td> <td>45,5 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Refinery - vessel inspections</td> <td>13</td> <td>29,5 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tunnel - general inspection</td> <td>18</td> <td>40,9 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tunnel - local inspection</td> <td>13</td> <td>29,5 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Viaduct - surveying target or s...</td> <td>12</td> <td>27,3 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Viaduct - visual inspection of...</td> <td>18</td> <td>40,9 %</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <p>Figure 8. Results of the 1st PILOTING workshop survey: Which PILOTING use cases are of most interest to industry?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which piloting subsystem are you mostly interested? 	Use Case	Count	Percentage	Refinery - ground monitoring	7	15,9 %	Refinery - inspection of large...	13	29,5 %	Refinery - pipe inspections	20	45,5 %	Refinery - vessel inspections	13	29,5 %	Tunnel - general inspection	18	40,9 %	Tunnel - local inspection	13	29,5 %	Viaduct - surveying target or s...	12	27,3 %	Viaduct - visual inspection of...	18	40,9 %
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<p>Autonomy in Aerial Robotics for inspection and maintenance workshop at ERF 2021</p>	<p>The motivation of the workshop is to embody Artificial Intelligence as a relevant characteristic of aerial robots for inspection and maintenance. In some applications the end-users prefer fully autonomous solutions, while in others the intervention of human pilots and other operators is preferred.</p> <p>On the other hand, energy autonomy referring to the time of flight and range, is a critical characteristic involved in the inspection of large infrastructures and plants. This is usually related to the size of the unmanned aerial vehicles and safety constraints, as well as the possibility to recharge</p>	<p>14th April</p>	<p>>100 attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 65% Scientific/research community (Universities, research centres, etc) 35% Industry/End- 	<p>This main outcome of this workshop was to get the insight of the industry and end-users about the level of autonomy that they expect in robotic vehicles in I&M applications. It was clear that the I&M sector is not looking forward fully autonomous robotic vehicles. However, for them it is important that the robotic vehicles offer a certain level of autonomy that allows for a safe and efficient operation, and also, allows that the operations do not require a very high level of specific skills.</p>																														

	<p>or substitute batteries, the ability to pilot the aerial vehicle Beyond the Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS) and the regulations.</p> <p>In the Workshop the existing technologies were analysed together with the end-users preferences . The Workshop has also presented recent results and demonstrations of relevant projects as PILOTING, HYFLIERS or AERIAL-CORE.</p> <p>This workshop was co-organized by PILOTING project where USE and FADA-CATEC presented new research results. In addition, the other organizers and speakers are top level members of research institutions and relevant companies including end-users (ENDESA-ENEL, CHEVRON, TOTAL) and technology manufacturers (THALES GROUP, Terabee), together with young representatives of start-up companies (VES, NEOBOTICS)</p>		users from I&M sector	This information and feedback were very relevant to PILOTING activities in order to push into the development of advanced autonomous functionalities but focused on increasing safety of the operations, and also, decreasing the ability and skills of the robotic vehicles' operators.
2nd PILOTING workshop: European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance	<p>The 2nd PILOTING workshop was oriented to present an overview of all active European Robotics & AI projects that apply Robotics and AI technologies to Inspection and Maintenance activities of any sector or application. The following projects were presented: PILOTING (https://piloting-project.eu/), RIMA (https://rimanetwork.eu/), AERIAL-CORE (https://aerial-core.eu/), METRICS (https://metricsproject.eu/inspection-maintenance/), ATLANTIS (https://www.atlantis-h2020.eu/), HYFLIERS (https://www.oulu.fi/hyflilers/), PANOPTIS (http://www.panoptis.eu/), DURABLE</p>	29 th June 2021	<p>>100 attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 55% Scientific/research community (Universities, research centres, etc) • 45% Industry/End- 	<p>This workshop served to identify possible synergies with other H2020 or European projects.</p> <p>For example, Bugwright2 was interested to know more about the PILOTING I&M platform and if it could be possible to use part of these software modules in their project. We are evaluating these options.</p> <p>Also, we identified other collaborations outside of PILOTING. For example, we have identified that Bugwright2 has a mock-up of a ship aerostructure that could be interesting for a</p>

	<p>(https://www.durableproject.eu/), BugWright2 (https://www.bugwright2.eu/), RAPID (https://rapid2020.eu/), RESIST (https://www.resistproject.eu/), ROBINS (https://www.robins-project.eu/), 5DAEROSAFE (https://5d-aerosafe.eu/), AERO-TRAIN (https://www.aerotraining.eu/), ROBOTICS4EU (https://www.robotics4eu.eu/) and OMICRON (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955269).</p> <p>Figure 11 shows the invitation email sent to PILOTING User group, partners and invited project list of contacts and social networks.</p>		users from I&M sector	<p>Spanish spin-off that is developing contact inspection solutions for ships in the framework of a RIMA DIH project. We have put them in contact.</p> <p>Moreover, these workshops also increases the network for creating new consortiums. As a concrete example, CATEC is in conversations with INESTEC (ATLATIS project coordinator) to present a new Horizon Europe in the next calls.</p>
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Table 11. Workshops organised within PILOTING project first perio

Figure 10. 1st PILOTING stakeholder's workshop agenda presentation.

PILOTING Consortium invites you to an **online workshop on June 29th**, as part of PILOTING project activities (<https://piloting-project.eu/>).

This Workshop will be oriented to present an overview of all active European Robotics & AI projects that apply Robotics and AI technologies to Inspection and Maintenance activities of any sector or application.

Then, it is a great opportunity to catch, in a single day, the leading innovative robotic technologies that are being developed for I&M industry.

The following projects will be presented:

- **10:00-10:15 Welcome**
- **10:15-10:30 Multidomain**
10:15-10:30 PILOTING <https://piloting-project.eu/>
- **10:30-11:15 Ships and Ports**
10:30-10:45 ROBINS <https://www.robins-project.eu/>
10:45-11:00 RAPID <https://rapid2020.eu/>
11:00-11:15 BugWright2 <https://www.bugwright2.eu/>
- **11:15-11:30 Electrical distribution**
11:15-11:30 AERIAL-CORE <https://aerial-core.eu/>
- **11:30-12:15 Civil Infrastructure**
11:30-11:45 RESIST <https://www.resistproject.eu/>
11:45-12:00 PANOPTIS <http://www.panoptis.eu/>

12:00-12:15 OMICRON <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955269>

- **12:15-12:30 Oil&Gas sector**
12:15-12:30 HYFLIERS <https://www oulu fi/hyfliers/>
- **12:30-12:45 Airports**
12:30-12:45 5DAEROSAFE <https://5d-aerosafe.eu/>
- **12:45-13:15 Renewable energy infrastructure**
12:45-13:00 DURABLE <https://www.durableproject.eu/>
13:00-13:15 ATLANTIS <https://www.atlantis-h2020.eu>
- **13:15-14:15 Promoting Robotics in I&M applications**
13:15-13:30 RIMA <https://rimanetwork.eu/>
13:30-13:45 METRICS <https://metricsproject.eu/inspection-maintenance/>
13:45-14:00 AERO-TRAIN <https://www.aerotrain-etn.eu/>
14:00-14:15 ROBOTICS4EU <https://www.robotics4eu.eu>
- **14:15-14:30 Conclusions and farewell**

You can register to the workshop using the following link:

<https://www.eventbrite.es/e/european-robotics-ai-workshop-applied-to-inspection-and-maintenance-tickets-157605647735>

*Workshop connection details will be sent by email previously to the workshop date.

**Workshop co-organised by the euRobotics Aerial Robotics and RIMA H2020 Project (through the Inspection and Maintenance, and Aerial Robotics Topic Groups).

Best regards,
Antidio Viguria
(PILOTING Project Coordinator).

Figure 11. Email invitation to the 2nd PILOTING Workshop.

3.4 PILOTING presentation at relevant events

Next, a brief description of the relevant events where PILOTING project has been presented.

EVENT	DETAILS	VENUE	DATE	INVOLVED INSTITUTIONS	Website
European Robotics Forum (ERF) 2020	On the one hand, CATEC has presented PILOTING project as one of the new H2020 projects during ERF 2020. Moreover, CATEC has had a stand and has disseminated PILOTING with a roll-up and flyers. On the other hand, ROBOTNIK was present in the ERF with a dedicated booth showing the capabilities of the company and the different R&D initiatives. Finally, USE and CATEC organized a workshop on I&M where the PILOTING project were presented (see Section 0).	Málaga, Spain	2-5 March 2020	CATEC RBNK USE	https://www.eu-robotics.net/robotics_forum/
EXPODRONICA 2020	CATEC has presented PILOTING project in an oral presentation during EXPODRONICA 2020. You can find it available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4RPJ4BDZgBA&t=1869s	Online	9-10 September 2020	CATEC	https://expodronica.com/
ICUAS 2020	A. Ollero. Keynote speaker "New aerial robotic manipulators for efficient and safe operation"	Online	September 2020	USE	http://www.uasconferences.com/2020_icuas/
S-MOVING 2020	S-MOVING is the reference space in Spain for companies, professionals, entities and public administrations in Intelligent, Autonomous and Connected Vehicles. In addition, this was the first physically event in Spain after the lockdown due to the Covid pandemic.	Málaga, Spain	31 September-1 October 2020	CATEC	https://smoving.fycma.com/

	CATEC had a stand and has disseminated PILOTING with a roll-up and flyers in front of a large audience (15600 attendees+exhibitors)				
IROS 2020	USE participated in the IROS 2020 Conference presenting PILOTING in the Workshop “Perception, Learning, and Control for Autonomous Agile Vehicles”	Online	2-3 November 2020	USE	https://wp.nyu.edu/workshopiros2020plc/
iMOV3D Industrial forum	Presentation of PILOTING project and some of its key technologies to Spanish companies (Airbus, Babcock, Everis, GMV, etc.)	Online	November 2020	CATEC, USE	N/A
CivilDron 20'	CATEC has presented PILOTING at CivilDron'20, which is one of the main references in the field of congresses in the drone sector, the event provides a 360° vision of what really interests the different types of participants from both the business world and public institutions.	Online	15-16 December 2020	CATEC	https://www.civildron.com/
ISTRAI-2021	ICCS presented a general overview of the PILOTING project at the 2 nd World Conference on Robotics & Artificial Intelligence (ISTRAI-2021) with the theme “Exploring the Research Challenges and Advancements in Robotics and Artificial Intelligence”. You can find the presentation available at the following link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=onk3xkAc-cl	Online	23rd March 2021	ICCS	https://kindcongress.com/event/2nd-world-conference-on-robotics-and-artificial-intelligence/
European Robotics Forum (ERF) 2021	The ERF 2021 edition was held as a virtual event. CATEC participated as goal sponsor and presented PILOTING in two different workshops: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – “Putting robotics co-creation into practice” workshop. – “Autonomy in Aerial Robotics for inspection and maintenance”, organised by USE and 	Online	13-15 April 2021	CATEC, USE	https://www.eu-robotics.net/robotics_forum/info/index.html

	PILOTING project (https://grvc.us.es/erf-aerial-robotics-workshop/)				
Sprint Robotics Programme Committee	Antidio Viguria, from CATEC, Thomas Krousarlis from INLECOM, Moritz Oetiker from WTR and Russell Brown, from CHEVRON, presented PILOTING project to Sprint Robotics Programme Committee.	Online	20 March 2021	CATEC, CHEVRON, INLECOM, WTR	N/A
ICRoM 2021	Conference related to robotics applications, and could be a potential choice for our partners that are working on these activities	Online	28-30 May 2021	ICCS	http://www.icrom.org/index.html
ICRA workshop	Resilience and long term autonomy for aerial robotics systems.	Online	30 May-5 June 2021	USE	https://www.ieee-icra.org/
Robotics and Artificial Intelligence Cross-Sectoral Innovation Conference (RAIC 2021)	Conference for the Norwegian I&M community. PILOTING has been presented as part of SINTEF presentation.	Online	8-9 June 2021	SINTEF	https://raic-2021.b2match.io/
18th IRF World Meeting & Exhibition	CATEC has submitted a paper which is waiting for acceptance notification	Dubai	7-10 November 2021	CATEC	https://worldmeeting.irf.global/

Table 12. PILOTING presentation at relevant events.

Figure 12. PILOTING presentation at ERF 2020.

Figure 13. PILOTING presentation at RAIC 2021.

3.5 Clustering with other projects and initiatives

Since the project's launching, we have successfully carried out cross-dissemination activities with other projects, enabling us to reach a wider margin of possible target audiences. We must highlight some of them due to their relevance and interesting effect. The list of relevant to PILOTING project is as follows:

➤ ATLANTIS

ATLANTIS (<https://www.atlantis-h2020.eu/>) is an H2020 project (ICT-2019-2-ID871571) that aims to establish a pioneer pilot infrastructure capable of demonstrating key enabling robotic technologies to inspect and maintain offshore wind farms.

ATLANTIS exposes the urgency to guarantee early access by medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), R&D institutions or energy operators to a pilot infrastructure for validating innovative and technological solutions with high potential.

In this case, PILOTING and ATLANTIS signed a MOU (Memorandum of understanding) to share best practices and lessons learnt related to the application of robotics to I&M sector to cross-disseminate each other events.

Also, ATLANTIS has been disseminated within PILOTING activities in different ways:

- It was included as an invited project in the [1st issue of the PILOTING newsletter](#).
- It was presented in the 1st workshop organised within the PILOTING project: "PILOTING's stakeholder workshop" (see Figure 14).

Figure 14. ATLANTIS project presentation at “PILOTING’s stakeholder workshop.”

- It was presented in the 2nd workshop organised within the PILOTING project: “European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance”.

➤ **RIMA**

Inspection and Maintenance (I&M) represents a large economic activity – global market estimated at 450 Billion Euro – spanning across multiple sectors. There is massive potential for robotic applications to increase productivity and improve safety, but robotics' total market size is still negligible concerning the overall market size.

RIMA (<https://rimanetwork.eu/>) is a 4-year H2020 project (DT-ICT-02-2018-ID 824990) aiming to tackle this gap by establishing a network of 13 Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) and industry associations to support the uptake of robotics – and help small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) to develop novel solutions for different industry sectors through 2 Open Call rounds (2019 / 2020) with a total amount of 8.1M€

PILOTING holds close coordination with RIMA.

Among other activities, it is worth noting that PILOTING provided support to RIMA by disseminating the information related to the 2nd Open Call in different ways:

- Including RIMA as an invited project in the [2nd issue of the PILOTING newsletter](#).
- Dissemination of RIMA 2nd open call through PILOTING social networks.

PILOTING Social Network	Date	Status	Link
Twitter	15/12/2020	Post	https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU/status/1338816958024867845

	16/12/2020	Post	https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU/status/1339149315697233920
	13/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/grvc_us/status/1349293047037759488
	14/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1349749832873873410
	14/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/RODIN_network/status/1349707702075871232
	15/01/2021	Post	https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU/status/1350038460451717126
	18/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/FADA_CATEC/status/1351093436477276161
	19/01/2021	Post	https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU/status/1351540210170003457
	20/01/2021	Post	https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU/status/1351850738016800773
	22/01/2021	Post	https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU/status/1352649393715949568
	23/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/FADA_CATEC/status/1352928311098404864
	25/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1353661894909947905
	26/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/FADA_CATEC/status/1353992518917124096
	28/01/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1354889519166795779
	09/02/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/FADA_CATEC/status/1359059769760378882
	10/02/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1359550873916104706
	25/02/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1364882520282697736
	04/03/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1367397086388514818
	05/03/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/RODIN_network/status/1367754530251800579
	11/03/2021	Retweet	https://twitter.com/NetworkRima/status/1370082466132803584
	15/12/2020	Post	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6744582803393912832

	15/01/2021	Post	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6757624386859081728
	22/01/2021	Post	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6758415236430082048
	25/02/2021	Repost	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6770687225429544960

Table 13. Promotion of RIMA in the PILOTING social networks.

- Dissemination of the 2nd open call through the PILOTING User Group (see Figure 15).

Dear members of PILOTING User Group,

We are pleased to inform you that the **RIMA 2nd Open Call is open!!!** Apply and you can receive up to 150K EU Funding!

RIMA is a 4-year EU-funded project (2019-2022) that aims to accelerate the **deployment of robotic technologies in inspection and maintenance (I&M) applications**. RIMA tackles this goal by establishing a network of 13 Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) and industry associations to support the uptake of robotics – and help small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) to develop novel solutions for different industry sectors.

Why apply?

- **VERY EASY** process for the SMEs to obtain European funds!!
- Opportunity to **bring your innovative technology closer to the market** (from TRL 5 to 7).
- Development of new products or services or innovate the existing ones.
- Opportunity to **enlarge your application field**.
- **Find complementary companies** to develop your innovative business together.
- **RIMA consortium will assist you** free of charge with Technical Services, Business Services and Mentoring Services

Applications to the 2nd Open Call will be accepted until the 17th March 2021 at 16:00 CET. For more information: <https://rima-opencall.fundingbox.com/>

APPLY NOW!!

You can find all the information about the 2nd open call available at: <https://rima-opencall.fundingbox.com/pages/doc>

Please, follow the project in its social media:

- <https://www.facebook.com/RimaNetworkEU>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rima-network/>
- <https://twitter.com/NetworkRima>

Below you can find the information related to **RIMA H2020 project**. We hope you find it interesting.

- ✓ RIMA supports financially and technically 50 cross-border experiments involving European Small and Medium-sized enterprises through 2 Open Call rounds (2019 / 2020) with a total amount of 8.1M€.
- ✓ During RIMA's 1st open call, we received 121 applications across Europe, out of which 19 projects from different industries were selected. The selected projects received funding and technical and business mentoring from the RIMA Project.
- ✓ The 2nd open call, closing in March 2021, will select up to 31 European Robotics. Each selected consortium will receive up to **€150.000 equity-free funding**, access to acceleration services, and expertise of the DIH network, all dedicated to help the innovation and commercialization process of new I&M robotics solutions in Europe.

Best regards, PILOTING coordination team

Figure 15. Email disseminated through the PILOTING User Group with RIMA information.

Furthermore, RIMA has been presented in both PILOTING's workshops organised in the first project period.

➤ **RESIST**

RESIST (<https://www.resistproject.eu/>) is an H2020 European project (MG-2017-Two-Stages-ID-769066) whose overall goal is to increase the resilience of seamless transport operation to natural and man-made extreme events, protect the users of the European transport infrastructure and provide optimal information to the operators and users of the transport infrastructure.

Within PILOTING, RESIST has been disseminated in different ways:

- Dissemination of RESIST H2020 project through the PILOTING User Group (see Figure 16 Figure 15).
- RESIST was presented in the 2nd workshop organised within the PILOTING project: “European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance”.
- The 1st “[PILOTING Inspection gadget](#)” podcast presents RESIST project.

Dear members of PILOTING User Group,

Below you can find the information related to RESIST H2020 project. We hope you find it interesting.

RESIST is an H2020 project that started on 1st September 2018 and aims to increase the resilience of seamless transport operation to natural and man-made extreme events, protect the users of the European transport infrastructure and provide optimal information to the operators and users of the transport infrastructure. RESIST will address extreme events on critical structures, implemented in the case of bridges and tunnels attacked by all types of extreme physical, natural and man-made incidents, and cyber-attacks. Its technology will be deployed and validated at two pilots in real conditions and infrastructures.

Social media: (RESIST project has already shared the information about the webinar on its social media) Twitter - @project_resist
LinkedIn – RESIST Project Stakeholder group:

- The RESIST Stakeholder group aims to engage companies, public authorities, road operators, research institutes and interested parties outside the consortium in the exchange of information, experience, and best practices with the project partners and other stakeholders.
- The Stakeholder group members will have the opportunity to provide requirements or feedback to the project, and will be regularly informed about RESIST news and progress.
- The Stakeholder RESIST is being established to generate active interest and motivate all relevant stakeholders to contribute to the RESIST work and ongoing discussions. It is anticipated that this will increase the adoption and sustainability of the RESIST findings, thereby leading to a wide market uptake of the developed technological solutions.
- The RESIST Stakeholder group is not an open public platform as only professionals and experts of relevant domains are invited.
- Your participation in the RESIST Stakeholder group is voluntary, free, and has no further obligations.

How to join to the RESIST Stakeholder Group?

If you are interested to be a member of the RESIST Stakeholder group, please register here:

<https://forms.gle/AixST5xMg7MRnxYMA>

Best regards, PILOTING coordination team.

Figure 16. Email disseminated through the PILOTING User Group with RESIST information.

➤ **AERIAL-CORE**

AERIAL-CORE (<https://aerial-core.eu/>) is an H2020 project (ICT-2019-2-ID- 871479) that will develop an integrated aerial cognitive robotic system that will have unprecedented capabilities on the operational range and safety in the interaction with aerial co-workers for applications such as the inspection and maintenance of large linear infrastructures. It will implement cognitive capabilities for perception and teaming, aerial morphing to combine long range endurance and hovering for local observations, manipulation involving force interactions, and co-working with humans.

Within PILOTING, AERIAL-CORE has been presented in the following ways:

- It was introduced in the 1st workshop organised within the PILOTING project: “PILOTING’s stakeholder workshop” (see Figure 17).

Figure 17. AERIAL-CORE project presentation at “PILOTING’s stakeholder workshop”

- It was presented in the 2nd workshop organised within the PILOTING project: “European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance”.

➤ METRICS

METRICS (<https://metricsproject.eu/>) is an H2020 project (ICT-09-2019-2020-ID- 871252) that will be focused on organising challenge-led robotics competitions in the four Priority Areas (PAs) identified in the topic ICT-09-2019-2020: Healthcare, Inspection and Maintenance, Agri-Food, and Agile Production. METRICS is designed to organise competitions as reproducible and objective evaluation campaigns and aims to structure in a sustainable way the European robotics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) community around the four PAs.

The following cross-dissemination actions between METRICS and PILOTING have addressed in this period:

- It was introduced in the 1st workshop organised within the PILOTING project: “PILOTING’s stakeholder workshop” (see Figure 18Figure 17).

Figure 18. METRICS project presentation at “PILOTING’s stakeholder workshop”

- It was presented in the 2nd workshop organised within the PILOTING project: “European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance”.

To finalise, it is important to highlight that within the cross-dissemination activities, others European projects were disseminated within the 2nd PILOTING workshop: HYFLIERS (<https://www.oulu.fi/hyfliers/>), PANOPTIS (<http://www.panoptis.eu/>), DURABLE (<https://www.durableproject.eu/>), BugWright2 (<https://www.bugwright2.eu/>), RAPID (<https://rapid2020.eu/>), ROBINS (<https://www.robins-project.eu/>), 5DAEROSAFE (<https://5d-aerosafe.eu/>), AERO-TRAIN (<https://www.aerotrains-etn.eu/>), ROBOTICS4EU (<https://www.robotics4eu.eu/>) and OMICRON (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955269>).

4. Monitoring of the KPIs

To complete the report addressed in the present deliverable, Table 14 summarizes the status of the KPIs after the first 18 months of the projects.

<i>Communication / Dissemination means</i>	<i>Targeted communities</i>	<i>Performance Indicators</i>	<i>Target Value</i>	<i>Reach level</i>	<i>Status</i>
Logo and Poster	General public	Logo and Poster designed	1 logo, 1 poster layout	International	Target achieved
Local media presence	General public	N° of appearances (TV, newspaper, radio, magazines)	One appearance per year per participating country	National	Achieved (see section 2.4)
Social media presence	General public	N° of posts performed, social media	One LinkedIn and one Twitter post	International	Post: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2020: Achieved • 2021: Ongoing

		metrics (N° of followers)	per week, 500 followers		Followers: 600 • Achieved
Content delivery platforms (e.g. YouTube)	General public	N° of channels, performed posts	Project channel in at least one delivery platform with a minimum of 3 posts per year	International	2020: Achieved • Video presentation of PILOTING project. • PILOTING partners' KOM interviews: 1st and 2nd part. 2021: Achieved • 3 PILOTING Youtube Series "Meet Our Inspection Robot" Episodes : Episode 1.- AeroX , Episode 2- CART Robot and Episode 3- BIKE • 5 PILOTING Podcast "Inspection gadgets": Episode 1. , Episode 2. , Episode 3. , Episode 4 and Episode 5.
Press releases	Industry, general public	N° of press releases issued	One press release per year per participating country	National and International	2020: Achieved (see section 2.4) 2021: Ongoing
Newsletters	Industry and Public Institutions	N° of newsletters released	2 newsletters per year	International	2020: Achieved (see section 2.52.4) 2021: Ongoing
Publications	Research and Industry	N° of papers published	> 10 peer-reviewed scientific journals and conference publications	International	Ongoing (3 published; and two with abstract accepted; see section 3.2)
PILOTING User Group	Industry	N° of participants	At least 100 members	International	Target achieved (already more than 210 members)
Clustering with other projects	Research and Industry	N° of projects collaborating with	RIMA DIH and at least three more projects	International	Achieved (clustering with 5 H2020 projects; see section 0)
PILOTING workshops	Industry and end-users	N° of workshops	At least three during the project	International	Ongoing (already organized 4 workshops; see section 00)

<i>Participation in relevant events</i>	End-users, standardisation bodies, public institutions, industry and research	N° of events per years	Participation in at least 2 events per year	International	2020: Achieved (participation in 7 events; see section 3.4) 2021: Ongoing (already participated in 7 events).
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Table 14. Dissemination and Communication KPIs

5. Conclusions

The deliverable D10.3 “First Mid-term Dissemination Report” has provided an overview of the main dissemination activities addressed by the PILOTING consortium, within the Dissemination plan defined in the D10.2 “Exploitation and Dissemination Plan”, during the first period of the project (M1-M18).

In this first period, the COVID-19 pandemic and its implications have been manifested in several aspects that have had a significant impact on the dissemination activities initially planned, such as carrying out research activities or holding physical events to improve the network of contacts.

However, the PILOTING consortium has done its best to move forward and do everything possible to ensure that the impact of the project will be maximised.

In this sense, PILOTING partners have a) fostered the development of the communication/dissemination tools defined in the D10.2, replacing the participation in physical events with online events, and b) developed new communication channels such as a: i) a YouTube series concerning the robotic vehicles which are being developing within the project or ii) a Podcast series with main actors of the I&M industry.

Thanks to the commitment of the PILOTING’s partners, all KPIs defined have been achieved in the first project period.

PILOTING consortium will continue working to disseminate the project and achieve the objectives defined in the D10.2. This deliverable is a living document that will be updated during the whole project and a new version will be submitted at the end of the next periods (second period, M36) and (third period, M48).

Annex I: Flyer layout

➤ 1st version

PILOTING PROPOSES

THE ADAPTATION, INTEGRATION, AND DEMONSTRATION OF ROBOTIC SOLUTIONS, IN AN INTEGRATED PLATFORM, WHICH WILL BE TESTED AND EVALUATED IN THREE LARGE-SCALE PILOTS: REFINERIES, BRIDGES/VIADUCTS AND TUNNELS WITH THE INVOLVEMENT OF ALL THE ACTORS THAT CONFORM THE FULL VALUE CHAIN.

CONSORTIUM

The PILOTING consortium is made of 14 high-profile European partners, from six European countries, carefully selected for their acknowledged excellence as well as both their complementarity and transnationality in order to provide the necessary knowledge, expertise, and state-of-the-art background required to ensure the success of the PILOTING project as well as the sustainability of the proposed research and expected results.

PILOTING consortium includes high reputation research and innovation partners together with worldwide leading technological companies, highly specialized SMEs, inspection and maintenance service providers and companies that operates or owns infrastructures on both considered sectors (Oil&Gas and Civil Infrastructures/Transport).

Therefore, PILOTING consortium integrates the full value chain of the inspection sector (from technological providers to inspection service providers and asset owners) ensuring the industrial application and future exploitation of PILOTING technological developments.

PARTNERS

CATEC, UIC, Chevron, ferrovial, Honeywell, Inspection Robotics, Applus+, EGNATIA ODOS, Quasert, SINTEF, inlecom, Robotnik

piloting_project.eu

EUROPEAN UNION
HORIZON 2020

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 871542

If you are interested in PILOTING project, please send an email to piloting-project@catec.aero to become a member of PILOTING User Group.

PILOTING_EU, CATECERO, H2020 PILOTING

ABOUT THE PROJECT

CURRENT EUROPEAN REFINERIES AND CIVIL INFRASTRUCTURES, LIKE TUNNELS AND BRIDGES, ARE AGEING, AND THEREFORE GRADUALLY BECOME DETERIORATED, ESPECIALLY TAKING INTO CONSIDERATION THE CURRENT AND FUTURE ECONOMIC SITUATION IN EUROPE WHERE LARGE INVESTMENTS IN RENEWING INFRASTRUCTURES ARE NOT FORESEEN.

Then, it is paramount important to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels in these ageing infrastructures. To overcome this important challenge, PILOTING proposes the adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform, which will be tested and evaluated in three large-scale pilots: refineries (Oil&Gas sector), bridges/viaducts and tunnels (Civil/Transport Infrastructure sector) with the involvement of all the actors that conform the full value chain.

The PILOTING integrated platform will demonstrate the application of robotics at scale in the domain of Inspection and Maintenance (I&M), reduce end-user commercial risks on the deployment of robotics in the sector, demonstrate capabilities and improve understanding of robotics uptake value, develop and support the related ecosystem around the piloting I&M operations, as well as, contribute to industrial standards in robotics for I&M.

CHALLENGES

THE MAIN FOCUS OF PILOTING PROJECT IS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY AND QUALITY OF INSPECTION AND MAINTENANCE ACTIVITIES IN ORDER TO KEEP THE NECESSARY SAFETY LEVELS IN AGEING INFRASTRUCTURES. TO ACHIEVE THIS INCREMENT, THE INSPECTION & MAINTENANCE INDUSTRY IS FACING THE FOLLOWING MAJOR CHALLENGES

CHALLENGE 1
Current inspection methodologies are based on manual inspection procedures which are low-speed and require, most of the times, infrastructures' shut-down. The use of robotic technologies in PILOTING will importantly decrease cost and time of inspection and maintenance.

CHALLENGE 2
Nowadays inspection authorities and personnel lack in using repeatable and reproducible inspection data, often found deficient in quality measurements. Errors in or limited quality of inspection measurement data can have important consequences that may lead to damages to the infrastructure or health risks to the public or infrastructure personnel. PILOTING will provide high precision measurement data (gathered by the robotic vehicles) structured and presented in a seamless but trustworthy approach towards the inspection personnel and maintenance teams following international and well-established reporting approaches.

CHALLENGE 3
Personnel access and probability of accidental falls and injuries represent the predominant cost of the inspection. Having personnel working on elevated structures and dangerous locations requires planning, presence of support personnel, which implicitly implies slow progress in the measurement operations. PILOTING will contribute to increase personnel safety through advanced and automated robotic systems.

OBJECTIVES

IN ORDER TO OVERCOME THE IDENTIFIED CHALLENGES, PILOTING HAS ESTABLISHED THE FOLLOWING OBJECTIVES

OBJECTIVE 1
Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence technologies to the end-users needs and increase their technological readiness levels for the three considered scenarios.

OBJECTIVE 2
Design and develop the PILOTING I&M open and scalable platform.

OBJECTIVE 3
Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological developments through large-scale pilots in real conditions and infrastructures.

OBJECTIVE 4
Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.

OBJECTIVE 5
Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

PILOTING PROPOSES

THE ADAPTATION, INTEGRATION, AND DEMONSTRATION OF ROBOTIC SOLUTIONS, IN AN INTEGRATED PLATFORM, WHICH WILL BE TESTED AND EVALUATED IN THREE LARGE-SCALE PILOTS: REFINERIES, BRIDGES/VIADUCTS AND TUNNELS WITH THE INVOLVEMENT OF ALL THE ACTORS THAT CONFORM THE FULL VALUE CHAIN.

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Therefore, PILOTING consortium integrates the full value chain of the inspection sector (from technological providers to inspection service providers and asset owners) ensuring the industrial application and future exploitation of PILOTING technological developments.

PILOTS FOR ROBOTIC INSPECTION AND MAINTENANCE GROUNDED ON ADVANCED INTELLIGENT PLATFORMS AND PROTOTYPE APPLICATIONS

PARTNERS

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OBJECTIVE 2

Design and develop the PILOTING I&M open and scalable platform.

OBJECTIVE 3

Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological developments through large-scale pilots in real conditions and infrastructures.

OBJECTIVE 4

Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.

OBJECTIVE 5

Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

Annex II: Roll-up layout

➤ 1st version

PARTNERS

➤ 2nd version

Annex III: Poster layout

➤ 1st version

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 871542

PARTNERS

OBJECTIVES

- OBJECTIVE 1**
Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence.
- OBJECTIVE 2**
Design and develop the PILOTING I&M open and scalable platform.
- OBJECTIVE 3**
Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological developments.

- OBJECTIVE 4**
Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.
- OBJECTIVE 5**
Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

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➤ 2nd version

OBJECTIVES

OBJECTIVE 1
Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence.

OBJECTIVE 2
Design and develop the PILOTING I4M open and scalable platform.

OBJECTIVE 3
Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological innovation.

OBJECTIVE 4
Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.

OBJECTIVE 5
Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

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